

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Decreasing water availability reduces productivity in Swiss forests along an altitudinal gradient

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Abstract

1. Forests are one of the most important terrestrial carbon sinks, but are increasingly under pressure due to drought, heat and the occurrence of extreme events. There are opposing longer term trends for European forest growth reported, and severe drought and disturbance events additionally impact forest ecosystems, so that the overall trend of forest productivity is uncertain.
2. Thirty years of harmonized forest monitoring at 18 forest sites along an altitudinal gradient in Switzerland provides a good basis for assessing the effects of climate change on forest conditions.
3. We found a decreasing trend of forest productivity (basal area index and net carbon uptake by growth), particularly pronounced since 2015 across all altitudinal ranges, age classes and species, which could not solely be attributed to stand density and ageing of the forest, but also to soil water availability and nitrogen deposition. The growth rate of trees, as well as the ingrowth rate, were hereby the most important factors explaining the overall forest productivity. At a given stand density, forest productivity was lower in recent years compared to earlier decades.
4. Overall, our results indicate a decreasing stand-level growth trend irrespective of site conditions and stand structure. This 30-year declining trend can be partly attributed to water and nitrogen availability, and points to a decreasing growth capacity of the forest sites that is the long-term potential of a site to sustain tree growth.
5. The pivotal role of water availability for sustainable forest production and the long-term effect of drought years on forest vitality urges us to rethink the adaptability of forests in view of the increasing frequency of drought and heat periods predicted for the future.

KEYWORDS

carbon uptake, dendrometer, drought, forest productivity, net primary productivity, stand density, tree growth

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1 | INTRODUCTION

Trees take up CO₂ from the atmosphere and continuously store temporally parts of the assimilated carbon in their woody biomass. One cubic metre of wood stores about 0.2–0.4 tons of carbon, depending on the tree species, which corresponds to about 1 ton of CO₂ absorbed (Guo et al., 2010). Forests therefore remove large amounts of CO₂ from the atmosphere and store it in wood and soil in the short to long term. Alongside the oceans, they are one of the most important terrestrial carbon sinks (Harris et al., 2021; Luysaert et al., 2010). Forests also help to cool the local and regional climate and provide protection against natural hazards, and deliver many other ecosystem services (Brockhoff et al., 2017). In recent decades, forests are under increasing pressure due to drought, heat and the occurrence of extreme events such as storms, forest fires and floods, as well as the spread of pests such as the bark beetle (McDowell et al., 2020). Recent reports of widespread forest dieback due to drought in Europe (Allen et al., 2010; Schuldt et al., 2020) have led to the conclusion that new innovative and alternative approaches are needed in forest management and nature conservation to build up climate resilient forests (IPPC, 2022; Krumm et al., 2020) for sustainably ensuring ecosystem services. Long-term monitoring data are an indispensable basis for assessing the effects of climate change on forest conditions and developing adaptation strategies for management (Achim et al., 2021; Larsen et al., 2022), as changes in stand-level biomass over time reflect key ecological processes—growth, mortality and recruitment—and serve as a valuable indicator for the assessment of forest condition and forest health (Dobbertin, 2005).

The effects of climate on forest growth are complex, often non-linear and influenced by local-scale factors (Bose et al., 2020). For example, warming combined with drought tends to reduce tree growth at lower elevations, whereas in colder environments—such as higher altitudes or latitudes—warming can enhance growth where it is otherwise limited by low temperatures (Dulamsuren et al., 2017; Jolly et al., 2005; Saxe et al., 2001). In addition to climatic conditions, the nutrient supply also plays an important role for tree growth (Spiecker, 1999). Nitrogen inputs initially can have a growth-promoting effect, but can turn to negative impacts on forest health once an oversupply is reached (Etzold et al., 2020). Nutrient availability can additionally strongly interact with soil water availability in affecting growth (Gessler et al., 2017). Furthermore, forest productivity is also modulated by forest age (Drake et al., 2011), stand structure (tree size and density; Zeller & Pretzsch, 2019) and species composition (Morin et al., 2018), and those can be altered by forest management (Dieler et al., 2017; Etzold et al., 2014).

In a review, Vacek et al. (2023) stated that the most significant consequences of climate change include more frequent and destructive large-scale forest disturbances, changes in tree growth rates and tree species migration, which have substantial effects on ecosystem carbon storage. While a recent synthesis reports increasing growth rates for Northern and Central Europe (Vacek et al., 2023), other studies showed growth declines within the last decades potentially

impacted by severe drought and disturbance events (Bose et al., 2025; Martinez del Castillo et al., 2022; Rohner et al., 2021; Rubio-Cuadrado et al., 2025). Given the multiple, intertwined and site-dependent driving factors, the overall development of forest growth and productivity is still associated with a large uncertainty in predictions of forest carbon sequestration potential (Pretzsch et al., 2023).

In the early 1990s, 18 long-term monitoring sites (also termed Level II sites) along climatic and environmental gradients, representing typical Swiss forest ecosystems, were established in Switzerland as part of the Swiss Long-Term Forest Ecosystem Research programme (LWF programme) and under the umbrella of the UNECE Co-operative Programme on Assessment and Monitoring of Air Pollution Effects on Forests (UNECE/ICP-Forests). Within this programme, several stand variables are assessed on a regular basis with harmonized methods to examine cause–effect relationships between the condition of forest ecosystems and various external influences, such as climate, nutrient and pollutant input. In the meantime, time series of up to 30 years, including forest productivity, stand characteristics, meteorological and nutrient conditions, are available. Although three decades are a relatively short period to fully understand forest dynamics, the recent decades marked by numerous extreme droughts have made this data invaluable (NCCS, 2018).

In this study, we examined the development of tree and forest productivity on those 18 Level II monitoring plots over the last decades and investigated which factors such as stand structure (tree density), age, climate and nutrients explain the growth of the main tree species and the productivity of the stands best. These plots are located along a large altitudinal gradient from lowland forests at 500 m a.s.l. up to mountain forests at almost 1900 m a.s.l., touching the tree line, and therefore experience very different climatic conditions (Figure 1). Specifically, we ask the following research questions: (i) How have stand volume, tree growth and forest productivity evolved at the LWF sites over the last three decades? Are there species and altitudinal differences? We hypothesize that productivity has decreased in the lowland sites due to the extreme drought events in the last decades, but that productivity increased in the higher altitudes due to increased temperatures. (ii) Which factors—demography, stand structure, climate, nutrients—explain the observed productivity trend most strongly? We hypothesize, that climate-driven changes in growth-rates do occur, but their expression is modulated by forest age and stand structure of the forests, resulting in regionally divergent productivity trends.

2 | METHODS

2.1 | Study sites and species

This study includes data from 18 long-term forest ecosystem research (LWF) sites in Switzerland (Figure S1). These monitoring sites were selected to cover representative forest ecosystems in Switzerland. Nine are coniferous forests, eight are deciduous forests and two are mixed forests, located along an altitudinal gradient of 500–1900 m a.s.l., and thus exposed to very different climatic conditions (Figure 1). There

FIGURE 1 Climatic conditions of the 18 Level II monitoring plots along an altitudinal gradient.

are seven warm and dry lowland sites, eight temperate and moist mid-elevation sites and four cool but dry high-elevation sites (Figure 1, Table S1). The forests also differ greatly in terms of stand density, age and species composition (Table S1). Despite this variability, European beech (*Fagus sylvatica* L.) is represented at nine sites with 3529 individuals, Norway spruce (*Picea abies*) at 14 sites with 4031 individuals, white fir (*Abies alba*) at 10 sites with 1996 individuals and Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris*) at seven sites with 3479 individuals (Table S2). Overall, 41 different tree species were recorded.

2.2 | Study design

The LWF study design combines long-term with temporary measurements of several forest compartments (Brang, 1997, and subsequent updates). Measurements are spatially arranged such that destructive and non-destructive measurements do not interfere. All measurements are conducted according to the manual of the UNECE/ICP-Forests Programme (Ferretti et al., 2017). Typically, an LWF site (usually with a size of 2 ha) is divided into two plots (each 1 ha) that include two subplots (0.25 ha, Figure S2). Each LWF site includes an area of intensive monitoring, where throughfall deposition and litterfall are sampled, and soil coring is conducted. Most of the LWF sites were established in the early 1990s, but some sites or plots were abandoned after 2014, while other sites were added later. Therefore, the length of the time series differs across sites and plots (Figure S3).

2.3 | Growth monitoring

Tree growth was assessed in two complementary ways: (i) spatially highly resolved (every tree), but with a lower temporal resolution

(5-yearly) (= DBH (diameter at breast height)-inventory), and (ii) since 2000, only few replicates (5–10 trees per dominant species) within one site, but with a higher temporal resolution (annually) (= DENDRO-inventory).

2.3.1 | Tree and forest growth with 5-yearly intervals (DBH-inventory)

Measurements

Diameter at breast height (DBH)-inventories took place during the non-growing season (typically October to April, depending on the site) in the years 1995, 1999, 2004, 2009, 2014, 2019 and 2022 +/- 1 year, resulting in inventory period intervals ranging from 3 to 6 years, on average 5 years.

The DBH was determined with manual circumference measurements with a calliper of every tree within the LWF plot with a DBH >12 cm, and of every tree within the LWF subplot area with a DBH >5 cm according to the LWF manual (Hug et al., 2011). Tree height was measured on all trees, or only on trees within the subplot area, depending on site and inventory. Further, tree status (alive/dead), stem breakage and wind-throw were recorded. For each site, control inventories were conducted within a few weeks of the original inventory, where all measurements were repeated on 5% randomly selected trees (Dobbertin & Neumann, 2010).

Calculation of tree and forest growth and C fluxes

We used basal area increment (BAI) at both tree and stand level and net primary productivity (NPP) at the stand level as response variables. BAI is derived directly from repeated DBH measurements and therefore carries relatively low measurement uncertainty. However, it represents growth at a single point of the tree stem and does not fully capture whole-tree or stand-level processes. In contrast, NPP integrates multiple components of biomass production and is based on allometric equations and several underlying assumptions. Although this introduces higher uncertainty, NPP provides a more comprehensive estimate of the carbon budget at the stand scale. It is particularly valuable for assessing the carbon sequestration potential of forests and for comparing productivity across sites, species or management regimes.

Basal area (BA) of a tree was calculated from DBH, and stem radial growth per tree was calculated as the stem basal area increment (BAI_{tree}) between two consecutive inventories (Table S3). Missing tree heights were gap-filled from species- and site-specific DBH–tree height relationships, derived from the available measurements and evaluated in Etzold et al. (2014). Based on DBH and partly tree height, the various tree compartments (stem and sapwood, roots, fine roots, branches and twigs, as well as leaves and needles) were estimated using allometric functions and, if available, validated with measured values (see Table S3 and Etzold et al., 2014). The timber stock of a forest is the sum of the stem wood (in $m^3 ha^{-1}$) of all living trees. The gross productivity of the forest (BM_{inv} , in $kg ha^{-1} year^{-1}$) is the sum of above- and below-ground tree growth between two inventories

divided by the time period (removals, such as cuttings and dead trees, are not considered for the gross productivity). Biomass (BM_{inv}) was converted into carbon uptake (net primary production, NPP_{inv} in $g\ C\ m^{-2}\ year^{-1}$), assuming that 1 kg BM corresponds to 0.5 kg carbon. In addition, the BAI of the forest (BAI_{inv} in $cm^2\ ha^{-1}\ year^{-1}$) was estimated as the sum of all BAI_{tree} within one inventory period. A total of 21,219 tree individuals were recorded during the entire period, of which approximately 3780 died or were felled during the monitoring period and approximately 3300 grew in again.

Mortality of the stand was calculated according to Sheil and May (1996) as follows:

$$M = \left(1 - \left(\frac{N_{survived}}{N_{was}}\right)^{\frac{1}{years}}\right) \times 100 \quad (1)$$

with M =annual mortality rate between two consecutive inventories in %, $N_{survived}$ =number of trees that survived between two inventories, N_{was} =number of living trees of the earlier inventory and $years$ =number of years between the two consecutive inventories.

Ingrowth was defined as the number of new ingrown trees divided by the inventory period in years.

2.3.2 | Calculation of annual tree and forest growth (DENDRO-inventory)

Since 2000, 5–10 trees of the dominant tree species were equipped with manual band dendrometers (Type D1, UMS, München, Germany), which were recorded annually, usually in October, when annual growth ceased (=DENDRO).

From the annual measurements of the DENDRO inventory, we interpolated from 2001 onwards the 5-yearly inventory data of the BHU-inventories to annual values. To test the representativeness of the DENDRO-trees for the whole plot, we compared the relative 5-yearly BAI of all trees within a LWF-plot with those of the DENDRO-trees. In most of the cases, there was a good agreement between both measures (median $r=0.73$), that is, both data series showed the same temporal variabilities. We then applied the relative annual changes in BAI of the DENDRO-trees to the NPP_{inv} per species, summed them up to the whole plot, and calculated the relative annual changes (=relative NPP_{yr} in %).

2.4 | Stand properties and environmental variables

Stand density index (SDI) was calculated from the number of trees per hectare and quadratic mean diameter (QDM) according to Reineke (Daniel & Sterba, 1980), with a constant value of -1.605 . We used the mean DBH of all trees per site and inventory as a proxy of stand ageing (mean DBH). Additionally, we have a rough stand age estimation done in the year 2000, which we used for the classification of young (on average 84 years), medium (143 years) and old forests (204 years).

Site-specific atmospheric nitrogen deposition (Ndep) was modelled for the year 1995 to 2020 at 5-year intervals (Rihm & Kuenzle, 2023).

Nitrogen and phosphorus concentrations in leaves and needles (folN, folP in mg/g dry weight) were determined every 2 years (Meusburger et al., 2025). For conifers, only the nutrient concentrations of the current year's needles were used, since results were similar for all needle age groups. To overcome species-specific differences in foliar nutrient concentrations, folN and folP were normalized per species. Soil chemical properties were measured in the beginning of the monitoring period (early 1990ies, Walthert et al., 2003), including soil pH and the carbon-to-nitrogen (C/N) ratio of the first 5 cm of soil. The 'effective' leaf area index (LAI) was derived from measurements done in the years 2011 and 2021 with a Plant Canopy Analyzer LAI 2000 (Licor, Inc.) and calculated according to Miller's (1967) equation as described in Thimonier et al. (2010).

Daily meteorological data (temperature, precipitation) per site were derived from (Meteotest, 2020). Soil water potential (SWP) was modelled by the process-based water budget model LWFBrook90 (R package LWFBrook90R, Schmidt-Walter et al., 2020). Although bi-weekly tensiometer measurements were available for the entire observation period, they do not capture dry soil conditions (below $-80\ kPa$) as water is withdrawn from the tensiometer under drier conditions. These dry ranges have only been resolved since 2020 through additional matric potential measurements using TensioMark sensors (ecoTech Umwelt-Messsysteme GmbH, Germany). The model was therefore calibrated to minimize bias between observed and simulated SWP, enabling the reconstruction of a temporally consistent time series spanning both wet and dry soil moisture conditions (Meusburger et al., 2022). From the meteorological and soil water potential data, we calculated mean, minimum and maximum values, and precipitation sums over the vegetation period (April–October), and aggregated them to the inventory periods. Additionally, we calculated deviations from the long-term averages (dT, dP, dSWP).

2.5 | Statistical analyses

All analyses, including statistical model runs and figures, were produced using the R statistical software (R Core Team, 2025). To account for age or tree size-related effects in growth trends, we examined the trajectories of temporal growth trends for three different DBH-classes. These DBH-classes were defined site-specifically since the age of equal sized trees can be very different depending on growing conditions. Three DBH-classes ('small', 'medium', 'large') with an equal number of trees with $DBH > 12\ cm$ were defined for all plots and subplots. Additionally, all trees within a subplot falling in the range of 5 to 12 cm were classified into an extra class ('sub').

To detect the temporal trend of the annual forest productivity (relative NPP_{yr}), we used mixed-effects models with year as fixed effect, and plot nested in site as random effects with the function *lme* of the package *nlme* in R (Pinheiro et al., 2025). To test for different temporal patterns depending on dominant species, altitude or age, we added the respective variable and its interaction with year to the fixed effects. To assess the temporal trend of inventory-based NPP_{inv} , mean growth rate (mean BAI_{tree}), mortality and ingrowth, year and

FIGURE 2 Tree density (Number *N* of trees per ha) versus the quadratic mean stem diameter (QMD) at the long-term monitoring sites. Each subplot is shown by one arrow, starting with the first inventory year and ending with the last one. Each dot represents one inventory year. The slope is calculated from the first to the last inventory year. The grey dotted lines show the self-thinning slope of -1.605 , as postulated by Reineke (Daniel & Sterba, 1980). Only trees larger than 12 cm are considered, also for subplots.

DBH-class as well as interactions among those variables were defined as fixed effects.

To assess which variables best explain the variability of inventory-based tree and forest productivity, we calculated the effect size of fixed-effect variables based on the coefficients generated by the mixed-effect models for three response variables including BAI_{tree} , BAI_{inv} and NPP_{inv} . For fixed effects on tree-level, we considered the tree DBH, SDI, mean DBH of the stand, DBH-class, long-term temperature (T) and precipitation (P) of the site, $Ndep$, and the deviation of temperature, precipitation and soil water potential during the vegetation period from the long-term mean (dT_{veg} , dP_{veg} , $dSWP_{veg}$), as well as interactions among those variables. For fixed effects on site-level, we considered the SDI, mean DBH of the stand, stand age in the year 2000, long-term temperature (T) and precipitation (P) of the site, altitude, $Ndep$, soil pH and C/N ratio, LAI, foliar N and P concentrations, and T_{veg} , P_{veg} , and SWP_{veg} and dT_{veg} , dP_{veg} and $dSWP_{veg}$, as well as interactions of meteorological variables with $Ndep$, T_{veg} and P_{veg} . We tested for collinearity in the models with the variance inflation factor. In case of collinearity ($vif > 4$), we checked which of the two collinear variables had the higher correlation with the response variable and kept this variable in the model. We started with the full model including all variables and interactions and removed those variables stepwise with the function *stepAIC* of the package *MASS* in R (Venables & Ripley, 2002) for which the Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC) was reduced the most, until no reduction in the AIC was obtained anymore.

For all models, we used squared-root or logarithmic transformation of the response variable if necessary to account for heteroscedasticity, and for mortality and ingrowth, with a lot of zero values, a zero-inflated model. Fixed effects were scaled so that mean=0 and SD=1. We included a correlation function (*corAR1*) in the model to account for temporal autocorrelation. Models were visually checked

for heterogeneity of variance and normality of residuals, and the conditional and marginal R^2 were calculated with the function *r.squaredGLMM* of the *MuMIn* package in R (Bartoń, 2025).

3 | RESULTS

In the year 2000, the mean age of the observed forests was 134 years, ranging from 60 to 235 years (Table S1). Over the 25–30 years of monitoring, most of the forests decreased in density (number of trees per ha) and increased in quadratic mean stem diameter (QMD) (Figure 2). The relationship between *N* trees per ha and QMD of most of the forest stands fell in the range of the proposed self-thinning line according to Reinecke (which has a slope of -1.605), indicating that competition-induced self-thinning balanced out new ingrowth. In some stands, the number of trees still increased. Few sites showed a larger mortality than expected from self-thinning, indicated by a steep decrease of tree density and resulting in a much steeper slope (red arrows in Figure 2).

3.1 | Temporal trend of forest productivity

The relative annual NPP_{yr} over all sites showed a significant negative trend over the last three decades (Figures 3 and 4a). Until 2010, the decadal average productivity was above average, with year-to-year fluctuations in productivity, which coincided well with the rel. SWP_{veg} and $T_{max,veg}$ conditions (years 1995–2010: $r=0.66$ for SWP_{veg} and $r=-0.79$ for $T_{max,veg}$; see also Figure S4). After the year 2012, however, there was a continuous decline of productivity, and after 2015, the productivity of many forest plots was below average (Figure 3). As the number of observational plots was decreasing

FIGURE 3 Relative NPP_{yr} and T_{max} during the vegetation period over the whole study period. Altogether 18 sites, 62 plots and subplots, and 972 measurement years were included. NPP_{yr} was derived from NPP_{inv} , which was interpolated to annual values by DENDRO-measurements. Dots indicate plot-wise values. The regression lines give the temporal trend of relative NPP_{yr} ($-0.01\%/year$, $p < 0.001$) and T_{max} , derived from mixed effects models with relative NPP_{yr} and T_{max} as response variables, respectively, year as fixed effect and plot nested in site as random effects. For the LMM, rel. NPP_{yr} was square root transformed to achieve normality. The grey polygon gives the number of plots that were included.

FIGURE 4 Predictions of linear mixed effects models with rel. NPP_{yr} as response variable and (a) year, (b) year and dominant species, (c) year and altitude and (d) year and age of the forest stand as fixed effects and plot nested in site as random effects. Rel. NPP_{yr} was square root transformed to achieve normality. The stars give the significance level of the fixed effect: *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$. See also [Figures S6](#) and [S7](#) for plots with measurement points included.

over time, we tested and confirmed this trend also for a subset of only those plots monitored over the whole time ([Figure S5](#)). The temporal variability of NPP_{yr} was significantly higher in later years

(2012–2022) compared to earlier times (2000–2011) (paired t -test, $CV_{2000-2012} = 0.087$, $CV_{2012-2022} = 0.162$, $p = 0.0015$). The decrease of NPP was most pronounced for plots dominated by *P. abies*, followed

by *Quercus* spp. and *Pinus* spp., and less for *F. sylvatica* (Figure 4b). The highest decrease of NPP_{yr} was found in the low altitudes, but also in the higher altitudes the decrease of NPP_{yr} was significant (Figure 4c). Considering different age groups, the decrease of NPP_{yr} was most pronounced in middle-aged forests (on average 143 years), while young (84 years) and old (204 years) forests showed the same slope of decrease (Figure 4d).

Decreasing productivity was confirmed also for the inventory-based calculation NPP_{inv} (Figure 5a). To account for an age effect, we did this analysis for four site-specific DBH classes (large, medium and small trees, and trees <5 cm (=‘sub’), which were only recorded on subplots). For all DBH classes, NPP_{inv} decreased over time, with the highest decrease in the subplot trees, followed by large, medium and small trees.

Mean growth rate per inventory (mean BAI_{tree}) also decreased over time for all DBH-classes, though it was not significant for subplot-trees (Figure 5b). Also, mortality showed a negative trend over time independent of DBH-class, and the steepest decrease was found for large trees (Figure 5c). Ingrowth for small and subplot-trees decreased (medium and large DBH classes have no ingrowth), and this was particularly pronounced for small trees (Figure 5d). We tested which variable, growth rate, mortality or ingrowth, was strongly related with NPP_{inv} , and its decreasing trend with a mixed effects model (Table S4). Growth rate (BAI_{tree}) was closely related to NPP_{inv} , with increasing effect size from subplots to small- to medium-sized trees and decreasing again for large trees. For medium and large trees, mortality rate was

an additional significant explanatory variable for NPP_{inv} , and for the subplot and small DBH-class it was ingrowth, respectively (Figure S8). Ingrowth was closely related to SDI, and $dSWP_{veg}$, indicating that ingrowth decreased in denser and older stands, but also due to drought (Figure S9).

3.2 | What explains the variability of tree and forest growth?

Linear mixed effects model with BAI_{tree} as response variable showed that—beyond the DBH of a tree—stand structure was most important in explaining the variability of BAI_{tree} (Figure 6). BAI_{tree} decreased with increasing SDI. Growth in medium-sized trees was larger than in young trees for all species. For beech, BAI_{tree} in large trees was even higher, whereas it decreased in large trees compared to the medium-sized trees in all other species. Mean climate conditions of the site (T and P) were not significant for BAI_{tree} as single predictors but were involved in interactions with $dSWP_{veg}$. For *Abies alba*, there was a significant interaction of dT and DBH-class, indicating a negative relation of temperature on growth, especially for the larger trees. For the other species, $dSWP_{veg}$ was more relevant for BAI_{tree} , with lower BAI_{tree} under drier conditions. This negative $dSWP_{veg}$ effect was more pronounced in larger trees and on generally warm sites (high T) for *F. sylvatica*, *Quercus* spp. and *P. abies*. *P. sylvestris* differed from the other species in showing

FIGURE 5 Predictions of linear mixed effects models with (a) rel. NPP_{inv} , (b) growth rate (rel. mean BAI_{tree}), (c) relative mortality rate and (d) relative ingrowth as response variable and year and DBH-classes as fixed effects and plot nested in site as random effects. Rel. NPP_{yr} was square root transformed to achieve normality. Ingrowth happened only in the two smallest DBH-classes (small for plots, sub for subplots); therefore, only two classes appear in (d).

FIGURE 6 Effect sizes of fixed effects of species-specific linear mixed effect models with BAI_{tree} as response variable and subplot nested in plot as random effects. BAI_{tree} was log-transformed to achieve normality. For fixed effects we considered the tree DBH, stand density index ('SDI'), mean DBH of the stand ('mean DBH'), DBH-class ('sub', 'small', 'medium', 'large'), long-term temperature ('T') and precipitation ('P') of the site, nitrogen deposition ('Ndep'), and the deviation of temperature, precipitation and soil water potential during the vegetation period from the long-term mean ('dT_{veg}', 'dP_{veg}', 'dSWP_{veg}'), as well as interactions among those variables indicated by '.'. The species-specific models were selected with backward selection based on AIC until no further decrease of AIC was achieved. Collinear variables were excluded from the analysis and are not shown in the figure. Also, non-significant relationships are not shown in the figure. Dots represent scaled coefficients with \pm SE. Marginal and conditional R^2 as well as number of observations and plots included per species are given in Table S5.

a positive relation of BAI_{tree} to $dSWP_{veg}$, and this effect was more pronounced on cool sites. The negative drought effect for *Quercus* spp. and *F. sylvatica* was more pronounced on drier sites (interaction $P:dSWP$), whereas it was the other way around for *P. abies*. Ndep was positively related to BAI_{tree} for all species, except *Quercus* spp., that is, higher growth on N-rich sites. There were also significant interactions of Ndep and $dSWP_{veg}$ for *Quercus* spp., *Acer/Fraxinus* and *P. sylvestris*, with a stronger growth reduction due to $dSWP_{veg}$ on N-rich sites.

SDI, Ndep, soil pH of the site and moisture conditions were the most important explanatory variables for BAI_{inv} on the stand level (Figure 7). Hereby, BAI_{inv} was higher under conditions with higher precipitation during the vegetation period and low $dSWP_{veg}$ (=moist). Stand-level NPP_{inv} showed the same relations as BAI_{inv} , but was not related to soil pH, but was additionally positively related to mean DBH and LAI.

Despite a large variability of NPP_{inv} versus SDI, the slope of this relationship decreased significantly over time within plots (Figure 8), meaning that forests in recent years showed overall a lower productivity at a given SDI at a given site compared to previous decades.

4 | DISCUSSION

We analysed tree growth and forest productivity data of Swiss forests over 30 years and found decreasing trends of NPP, independent of tree size, forest age and altitude. The decrease of NPP was mainly driven by a reduced growth rate of adult trees and abundances of ingrowth, and could be related to stand structural parameters, such as SDI and tree/forest age, but also to soil moisture conditions and nitrogen availability.

4.1 | Decreasing tree and forest productivity

Over the monitoring period of 25 to 30 years, tree mortality across most of the sites was within the range of self-thinning, that is, forest trees grew thicker, and number of trees decreased, but for some forest stands tree number also increased. Overall, the SDI increased still for most of the forest sites, resulting in increased timber volume. For two sites, the observed mortality was higher than expected through self-thinning. This was a very dry site in the Rhone Valley, for which high drought-induced mortality for Scots pine

FIGURE 7 Coefficients of fixed effects of linear mixed effect models with BAI_{inv} and NPP_{inv} as response variables and subplot nested in plot as random effects. The models were selected with backward selection based on AIC until no further decrease of AIC was achieved. Collinear variables were excluded. Bars represent coefficients with \pm SE. The models explain variability to 0.69/0.90 (mR^2/cR^2) for BAI_{inv} and 0.83/0.93 for NPP_{inv}, respectively.

trees was reported already in the early 2000s, and where a species shift from pine to oak is being observed (Hunziker et al., 2022; Rigling et al., 2013). At another site with exceptionally high mortality, many trees were infected by a root-rot fungus (Dobbertin et al., 2001). Despite the low mortality rates for the other forest sites, we observed an overall decreasing productivity over extended gradients of environmental conditions, forest ages and stand structures and species. This indicates that this pattern is not only a local phenomenon but rather follows a general trend. Tree growth usually declines at higher DBH (Anderson-Teixeira et al., 2022, and references therein), but the homogenous response across all DBH-classes indicates that the decrease cannot be solely attributed to an age effect.

Particularly after 2015, productivity decreased in most of the sites and stayed below average for the following years. This is confirmed by tree level stem radius change data from approximately 50 sites across Switzerland measured by point dendrometers, which also show a pronounced decreasing annual growth trend for *P. abies*, *P. sylvestris* and *F. sylvatica* from 2012 onwards (Bose et al., 2025). Also, data from the 5th National Forest Inventory (NFI) survey from 2018 to 2022 in Switzerland and the 4th National Forest Inventory in Germany in 2022 show decreasing productivity and timber volume in many parts of Switzerland (Abegg et al., 2023; Strauss & Fischer, 2025), and in Germany, especially for coniferous forests (BMEL, 2025), respectively.

Interestingly and contrary to our hypothesis, also in higher altitudes, the productivity decreased, though not that much as in the lowlands (Figure 4c). Some years ago, it was predicted that temperature-limited higher altitude forests might generally benefit from warmer temperatures and lengthening of the vegetation period

going along with climate change. Such altitude-dependent growth patterns were, for example, observed in Jolly et al. (2005) and modelled by Trotsiuk et al. (2021) for the extreme heat summer 2003 in Europe. However, our data do not support this hypothesis for recent years, but rather the finding that it is not the length of the growing season itself that is decisive for tree productivity, but rather the prevailing growth conditions and thus the number of days within the growing season on which the trees can grow, which are mainly determined by moisture conditions (Etzold et al., 2022). Negative effects on net carbon exchange due to climate change were already observed at high altitudes in Switzerland due to atmospheric (vapour pressure deficit) and soil drought (Gharun et al., 2020; Shekhar et al., 2024). It is also remarkable that the temporal stability of NPP decreased after 2012 compared to earlier years, meaning that the year-to-year variability is getting much higher. This variability poses a high uncertainty factor for wood production and is a great challenge for sustainable forest management. In general, the forest area in the Alpine regions continues to expand due to agricultural abandonment, although this expansion has slowed compared to previous decades (Abegg et al., 2023; Strauss & Fischer, 2025).

Decrease of the forest NPP for medium and large-sized trees was mainly driven by the lower growth rate of the trees, and for larger DBH-classes additionally by mortality. For small DBH-classes, ingrowth of new trees was the most important predictor for NPP. This pattern reflects typical demographic processes: old trees die, young trees grow in. However, ingrowth decreased significantly over the monitoring period, which was mainly related to denser, and therefore darker, and older forests, but also to less soil water. A negative impact of soil drought on recruitment was also observed for Douglas fir and beech by Dietrich

FIGURE 8 NPP_{inv} in relation to SDI for different inventory periods. Black lines show predictions of the linear mixed model for the years 2000, 2010 and 2020 with NPP_{inv} as response variable, SDI and year as fixed effects, and plot nested in site as random effects. NPP was square root transformed to achieve normality. The model had a marginal R^2 of 0.29 and a conditional R^2 of 0.63. The shaded area indicates the 95% confidence interval of the model fit.

et al. (2024), whereas Käber et al. (2021) did not find a clear impact of water relations on tree recruitment of temperate forests. Given this rather mixed evidence for the interrelationship between soil drought and tree recruitment in the current literature, our work that clearly identifies water availability in addition to stand structure as an important driver for tree recruitment should be an incentive for additional continental scale studies. Also, the mortality rate showed a decreasing trend. This is mainly an effect of the storm Lothar in 1999, which caused an exceptionally high mortality rate in the year 2000 in Switzerland (Usbeck et al., 2012). Excluding this year, the mortality rate showed no significant trend over time anymore (data not shown).

4.2 | Possible reasons for decreasing tree productivity

NPP of the forests was significantly related to the growth rate of the trees (BAI_{tree}). As expected, individual tree growth decreased with increasing stand density due to competition for space, light and other resources (Li et al., 2022) and increased with tree DBH (Figure 6). Beside this, we also found BAI_{tree} being related to climatic conditions. Available soil water (soil matric potential, $dSWP_{veg}$) decreased

over the monitoring period, whereas temperature increased at all sites (Figure S4). We found strong indication that BAI_{tree} is reduced by low soil moisture for most of the species, as was also reported by Vanoni et al. (2016) based on tree ring analyses. This finding is in line with the strong tree growth response to soil water on hourly (Zweifel et al., 2021), daily (Etzold et al., 2022) and to a lesser extent on weekly time scales (Bose et al., 2025). As $dTemp_{veg}$ and $dSWP_{veg}$ were highly correlated only one of both variables could be considered in the mixed-effect models. BAI_{tree} of *A. alba* was decreased by temperature, whereas BAI_{tree} of other species was more closely related to $dSWP_{veg}$. *A. alba* is usually occurring on relatively moist sites. This might be the reason why the temperature effect was higher for this species compared to soil moisture. For *P. abies*, *Fraxinus/Acer* spp., *Quercus* spp. and *F. sylvatica* BAI_{tree} was decreasing with drier conditions, but with site-specific variations, depending on annual temperature and precipitation. *P. abies* is known to be drought-sensitive and suffered from recent drought events in many parts of Europe (Popa et al., 2024; Ray et al., 2025). Accordingly, it showed the strongest decrease of NPP_{yr} among the studied species (Figure 4b). Interestingly, *P. abies* showed stronger growth reductions not only at warm, but also at moist sites. We explain this result by the fact that the warmest sites for *P. abies* had also the highest annual precipitation and there, the

impact of temperature outweighs the positive effect of abundant precipitation. For the other species, the drought effect of $dSWP_{veg}$ was most pronounced at warmer and drier sites. A high susceptibility of *F. sylvatica* to drought and heat was already observed after the heat year in 2018 (Braun et al., 2021), particularly on shallow south-exposed slopes (Rohner et al., 2021). We interpret our model results that beech has probably reached its stress limit with increasing drought and heat across Switzerland, even on sites with deeper soils as for the LWF sites. This is also confirmed by projections indicating that beech could reach its tolerance limit in extended areas across Switzerland in the long run and may no longer find suitable climatic habitat and growing conditions even with moderate future climate changes (Trotsiuk et al., 2021). As a consequence, it might lose significant parts of its distribution area in the long term (Gessler et al., 2024).

Pinus spp. showed, in contrast to all other species, a positive relationship of BAI_{tree} and $dSWP_{veg}$. We explain this pattern with the high altitude of many of the pine sites included in this study at the upper end of the altitudinal gradient, where growth is still rather limited by low temperatures and not primarily by soil moisture. Furthermore, the conditional R^2 of the model for *Pinus* spp. indicates a large site-to-site variability. Additionally, two of the four pine-dominated sites are those with increased mortality during the 2000s, which adds further dynamics to the actual growth processes.

Most species showed a positive relation of BAI_{tree} to N_{dep} , particularly pronounced for *Pinus* spp. and *P. abies*, both species growing at high altitudes and N-limited sites. We found a stronger $dSWP_{veg}$ effect at N-rich sites, indicating that trees at N-rich sites are growing faster but are also more susceptible to drought events, as reported for spruce by Tresch et al. (2023) and for beech by Dietrich et al. (2025). High N deposition has been associated with reduced root-to-leaf area ratio and increased canopy conductance, changes in the fine-root morphology and mycorrhizal communities, which may reduce the water uptake capacity and increase the risk of hydraulic failure under drought conditions (Poorter et al., 2012).

At the individual level, tree size significantly influenced tree responses to drought. We found that larger trees of *F. sylvatica*, *P. abies* and *A. abies* react more sensitively to drought and heat stress than smaller trees. Larger trees, with their increased solar exposure and water transport pathways, are generally more susceptible to drought (Bennett et al., 2015), and small trees are essential for offsetting productivity losses of large trees due to drought and other disturbances (Neumann et al., 2022). However, there are also tree species for which larger trees have an advantage under dry conditions. In particular, larger trees of slow-growing species with a high dry weight of leaves are better adapted to drought than smaller trees (Hanby et al., 2025).

4.3 | Possible reasons for decreasing forest productivity

The overall plot-based BAI_{inv} and NPP_{inv} variability could be best explained by SDI, N deposition and moisture conditions (as indicated by $dSWP_{veg}$ and P). Plot level productivity increased with SDI, that is, the

denser the forest, the more wood is produced despite lower growth rates of the single trees. It is generally known that forest growth initially increases with increasing stand density until a site-specific limit has been reached, above which growth cannot be increased further due to resource limitations and competition (Pretzsch, 2009). Modelling NPP_{inv} as a response of time and SDI (accounting for site differences), we found that NPP_{inv} generally increased with SDI over the monitoring period, but that the slope of this relationship became smaller in recent years (Figure 8). This may be attributed to other confounding factors, such as an ageing effect, but the model did not change significantly when including mean DBH as a proxy of the forest age (data not shown). Also, monitored forests belong to very different age classes with young forests included. We interpret this pattern rather as an indication that the growth capacity of the monitored forests appears to have declined for a given SDI in recent years, possibly due to decreasing water and nutrient availability. This is confirmed by studies showing that medium-dense forests are best protected against drought and heat (Sterck et al., 2021). Also, Bottero et al. (2017) and Andrews et al. (2020) recommend reducing competition for resources by thinning stands to make forests more resistant to increasing heat and drought. However, also adverse effects of thinning on the tree drought resistance have also been observed, particularly at typically well-watered sites, likely due to above-ground structural overshoot (Gessler et al., 2026). In our study, BAI_{inv} and NPP_{inv} were both clearly related to soil moisture conditions and precipitation, even over this extended gradient of site conditions, species and integrating a time-period of 5 years. This underlines the central role of water availability for sustainable forest production, the long-term drought effects on forest vitality and forces us to rethink the adaptability of forests in view of the increasing frequency of drought and heat periods predicted for the future.

5 | CONCLUSIONS

The growing conditions of our native tree species are increasingly changing. Rapid climatic changes make it difficult for long-lived organisms such as trees to adapt or acclimate. Thirty years of forest growth monitoring show climate-induced changes in growth and stand structure in the 18 monitored forest sites across Switzerland. The strong negative growth trends not only in the lowlands but also at high altitudes are alarming, as they cannot be attributed solely to an ageing effect. This decline in productivity is significantly related to stand structure parameters such as SDI, but also to soil water availability. Growth trends of this magnitude can have negative impacts on forestry yields, but also on the protective function of forests and further ecosystem services. Nevertheless, it should be emphasized that growth is only one aspect of the carbon cycle of a forest stand. Large amounts of carbon are still stored in the soil, which are released through microbial respiration and whose dynamics and magnitudes can change significantly depending on climate change (Guidi et al., 2022; Prietzel et al., 2016). As for today, forests are one of the most important carbon sinks. Forest management faces the major challenge of adapting

forests comprehensively to secure their capacity as a carbon sink and to ensure other ecosystem services such as protection against natural hazards or the recreational function. Silvicultural measures such as diversifying species composition, adjusting mixture patterns and regulating stand structure and rotation length will become increasingly important. Thinning, in particular, offers an effective means of reducing stand-level water demand and mitigating drought stress. However, its application must account for the long-term environmental context of the site to prevent unintended consequences, particularly those associated with overbuilt crowns (Gessler et al., 2026). Overall, the monitoring results highlight that future forest management must shift from optimizing for maximum productivity towards fostering structural and functional resilience. This includes promoting heterogeneous stand structures, ensuring sufficient growing space, and selecting species and provenances capable of withstanding more frequent and severe climatic extremes.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Arthur Gessler, Marcus Schaub, Katrin Meusburger, Anne Thimonier and Peter Waldner collected the data; Sophia Etzold ran the analyses, wrote the first draft, prepared the figures and finalized the manuscript. Arun K. Bose, Frank Krumm and Roman Zweifel discussed results, revised and edited the manuscript. All authors contributed critically to the drafts and gave final approval for publication.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Data are available from www.envidat.ch: <https://www.doi.org/10.16904/envidat.760> (Etzold et al., 2026).

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of this article.

Table S1. Stand properties of the 18 LWF sites.

Table S2. Tree species and number of recorded individuals and number of sites.

Table S3. Allometric functions to calculate tree volumes and biomass.

Table S4. Coefficients of the fixed effects of LMMs with rel. NPP_{inv} as response variable and growth rate (mean BAI_{tree}), ingrowth and mortality rate as fixed effects, and plot nested in site as random effects, calculated for different DBH-classes (sub, small, medium, large). Rel. NPP_{inv} was logarithmic transformed to achieve normality. 'n.s.' means not significant in the model, '-' means not included in the model. mR² and cR² indicates the marginal and conditional R² of the model, respectively.

Table S5. Marginal (mR²) and conditional R² (cR²) of final species-specific models explaining BAI_{tree} (Figure 6), and number of included observations and plots.

Figure S1. Location of the LWF-sites in Switzerland. The underlying map shows the long-term mean annual precipitation from 1991 to 2020, derived from MeteoSwiss.

Figure S2. Study design of LWF-sites. Each LWF-Site consists of one or two plots and subplots.

Figure S3. Observation years and inventory periods of the monitored sites and plots. Each colour represents a site, solid lines indicate a plot with measurements of trees with BHD >12 cm, dashed lines indicated subplots with measurements of trees with BHD >5 cm.

Figure S4. Temporal trends of relative SWP (a) and Tmax (b) at the LWF sites. The slope indicates the slope of the linear fit, derived from

mixed effect models with 'year' as fixed effect and 'plot' as random effect.

Figure S5. Relative NPP_{yr} and T_{max} during the vegetation period over the whole study period. Only those plots were included that were measured from the beginning to at least the year 2018. Altogether, we included 14 sites, 34 plots and 868 measurement years. NPP_{yr} was derived from NPP_{inv}, which was interpolated to annual values by DENDRO-measurements. Dots indicate plot-wise values. The regression lines give the temporal trend of NPP_{inv} (−0.012% per year, $p < 0.001$) and T_{max}, derived from mixed effects models with NPP_{inv} and T_{max} as response variable, respectively, with year as fixed effect and plot nested in site as random effects. The grey polygon gives the number of plots that were included.

Figure S6. Observations and predictions of linear mixed effects models with rel. NPP_{yr} as response variable and dominant species of the forest stand as fixed effects and plot nested in site as random effects. Rel. NPP_{yr} was square root transformed to achieve normality.

Figure S7. Predictions of linear mixed effects models with rel. NPP_{yr} as response variable and altitude (left column) or age group (right column) of the forest stand as fixed effects and plot nested in site as random effects. Rel. NPP_{yr} was square root transformed to achieve normality.

Figure S8. Fixed effects of LMMs with NPP_{inv} as response variable and growth, ingrowth and mortality rate as fixed effects, and plot nested in site as random effect. One separate model was calculated for each DBH-class, which are indicated by different colours. See also Table S4.

Figure S9. Predictions of zero-inflated mixed effects models with annual ingrowth as response variable and dSWP_{veg} and SDI as fixed effects and plot nested in site as random effects. Included were only subplots, where trees also between 5 and 12 cm are assessed. The model has a marginal R² = 0.27 and conditional R² = 0.68 and was selected as the best model based on AIC from a full model considering SDI, mean DBH, dSWP_{veg} and dT_{veg}, as well as interactions.

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